

Keys to Scandinavian Development and Its Applicability in the Latin American Context

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High social trust, healthcare and educational security, relatively low crime, and low unemployment—all products of the welfare state—provide citizens of the Nordic countries with the possibility of concentrating on their families, friendships, and self-realization, ensuring a high degree of well-being, which consistently positions them at the top of global happiness rankings. With Finland leading for the fifth consecutive year, Denmark, Sweden, and Norway rank second, fourth, and seventh respectively (Hunter, 2024). This panorama gives rise to the question of how the Nordic countries achieved such a stable economic system—having been among the poorest societies in Europe during the nineteenth century (Blomström & Meller, 1990)—and how Latin America might follow their example in order to attain the long-sought prosperity.

The economic development process of a country can be explained through the theory proposed by Walt Whitman Rostow in his seminal work *The Stages of Economic Growth* (1960). Therein, Rostow describes the transition from a traditional society to a modern, prosperous economy through five sequential stages. The first stage, the traditional society, is characterized by low productivity, subsistence agriculture, and rigid social structures, where growth is constrained by factors such as rudimentary technology, low investment, and high birth rates. The second stage, the preconditions for takeoff, is defined by changes that establish the foundations for sustained economic growth, including the development of infrastructure, education, and agrarian reforms. In the third stage, the takeoff, rapid economic growth occurs driven by one or two leading sectors, sustained by investment, innovation, and market expansion. The fourth stage, the drive to maturity, is characterized by economic diversification and expansion into new sectors, with sustained but slower growth. Finally, in the age of high mass consumption, society attains a high standard of living and widespread consumption of goods and services, with an economy based on a broad range of industries and sectors.

In order to examine the determinants of economic takeoff in the Scandinavian region in accordance with the stages of Rostow's development model, it is pertinent to investigate and analyze the role of economic liberalism, industrial development, educational policies, the relevance of private property, and the role of the welfare state in these countries. This analysis will be conducted in comparison with four Latin American nations: Colombia, Ecuador, Chile, and Uruguay.

1. Natural Resources and Infrastructure for Industrialization

The origins of Scandinavian development date back to the early nineteenth century and are rooted in natural resources—including iron, timber, dairy products, meat, cereals, and others. Denmark and Sweden were the first countries to drive an industrialization process based on these commodities, which enabled the export success that fostered the refinement of their production and resulted in the creation of forward and backward linkages, such as the paper industry and extractive machinery.

Specifically, the economic development of Denmark in the late nineteenth century was grounded in the principles of *laissez faire*, *laissez passer*, operating as an open economy with a very limited public sector. Its growth was based on the export of agricultural products with added value, such as butter, bacon, and cheese. To this end, small local institutions were established through a cooperative savings bank, which granted low-interest loans—with high repayment guarantees—to finance the construction of small dairies on family farms. (Paldam, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990)

The new wealth, which did not arise under centralized planning, led to rapid industrialization. A self-sufficient economy was never proposed, given Denmark's lack of natural resources such as minerals, fruits, and vegetables; consequently, its economy grew within a free trade system that had existed since the Viking era. (Randsborg, 1981)

It was not until the mid-twentieth century, however, that Denmark achieved one of the fastest growth rates in the world, thanks to the increase in public consumption and a housing construction boom, entering the third stage of Rostow's development model. Today, although industry is not strongly developed in Denmark, the tertiary sector is, with commercial conglomerates as its dominant firms.

Similarly, the evolution of the Swedish economy up to 1890 was driven by exports, resulting from external demand for goods, which led to an expansion of investment that brought with it a railway network that came to represent 3% of GDP. There was likewise a construction boom and an expansion in textiles, breweries, and flour mills (Blomström & Meller, 1990, Chapter 2, p. 35). As a consequence of the development process, an industry was established and Sweden's internal demand increased, resulting in a process of import substitution.

In the initial phases of Swedish development, family trading houses played an essential role in the financing and establishment of industries. These houses became provincial banks, whose system permitted the establishment of a stock exchange in Stockholm in the 1860s. (Blomström & Meller, 1990, Chapter 2, p. 38)

The Nordic countries' export boom has continued to grow to the present day, as evidenced by Graph 1. With Sweden at the forefront, the export gap between European and Latin American countries reveals a fundamental factor that has impacted the lack of growth in South American economies.

Furthermore, the added value on exports generated by industrialization in the Nordic countries persists to this day, with Graph 2 illustrating the significant difference between the primary export-oriented South American economies and the manufacturing share of Denmark, Sweden, and Finland.

This model of Scandinavian takeoff demonstrates that the foundations for industrialization were free trade, a liberal credit policy, and the transformation of raw materials to provide added value. This stage of development also relied on investments in infrastructure, the importation of foreign technology, and the formation of human capital. (Hveem, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990)

These were the elements that enabled sustained sectoral production growth in Sweden, particularly in manufacturing, commerce, and transport, until the mid-twentieth century, when the public

administration sector surpassed the others with the establishment of the welfare state and the consolidation of the final stages of Rostow's development model.

2. Education

In Denmark, the school reform of 1814 introduced universal primary education, while by the mid-nineteenth century low-cost adult residential schools were established, offering courses in general culture as well as instruction on topics of agricultural interest. (Paldam, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990)

The Danish reform, in line with similar initiatives in the region, gave the Nordic countries a significant advantage in terms of human capital in comparison with numerous other countries. As Graph 4 demonstrates, although Latin American countries are approaching the Scandinavian levels in terms of population with some degree of formal education, the latter have been at the forefront of education for slightly over a century.

Similarly to Denmark, in the 1870s, Swedish education shifted from a theological and bureaucratic emphasis to a scientific and technical one, with the creation of polytechnic universities to train engineers and business administrators.

According to Södestern, cited in Blomström & Meller (1990), Swedish industrialization and productivity owe their strength to the importance of engineering, with competitive innovations both nationally and internationally that emerged as a result of the educational emphasis and the importation of foreign techniques. It is no coincidence that illustrious inventors such as De Laval, Nobel, Wenström, and Dalén—inventors of the impulse steam turbine, dynamite, three-phase electrical energy, and lighthouse lighting, respectively—were Swedish. This pattern persists to this day, as evidenced by Graph 5.

Accordingly, the manufacturing of technology and machinery as a result of investment in human capital leads to greater productivity. This increase in marginal productivity translates into an increase in real wages and a reduction in working hours, as shown in Graph 6.

Additionally, one of the basic principles of the Nordic labor and educational market has been the promotion of labor mobility through employment centers, occupational education for adults, and robust relocation incentives that encourage regional mobility.

3. Private Property and Agrarian Reform

In Denmark, according to Paldam (cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990), the basis of economic growth in the late nineteenth century was the emergence of a new middle class, as a consequence of the abolition of serfdom in 1788, which allowed for social mobility since serfs could purchase land from the nobility. Thus, the vast majority of the new entrepreneurs were properly Danish and of the most diverse social origins. This doubled the volumes of commercial exchange.

In Finland, thanks to the land laws of 1922—a relatively recent date in comparison with its Scandinavian neighbors—all landless citizens with some minimal agricultural training were entitled to land.

These agrarian reforms, which incentivized an equitable distribution of land, along with a culture of respect for private property, sustained by the strength and transparency of institutions and

efficient property registries (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012), resulted in the highest indices of property security in the world. In particular, Finland presents the highest percentage of respondents who feel secure about land tenure (94%), followed by Sweden (92%), Denmark (92%), and Norway (91%). In contrast, the percentages for Colombia, Ecuador, Chile, and Uruguay are 65%, 69%, 72%, and 80% respectively.

These indicators in the Nordic nations translate into high levels of trust and investment, both nationally and from abroad. This, combined with high production and a trade balance with a surplus tendency, guarantees a high GDP. This high level of national income secures the wealth that is redistributed by the welfare state.

4. The State

In Denmark, 'No less than 30% of GDP is transferred to make income distribution more equitable' (Paldam, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990, Chapter 4, p. 83).

After all, the Nordic economic profession has been dominated since the past century by Keynesianism, combining the liberal economy with a welfare state which, according to Paldam, cannot exist without the free market.

In this mixed economy, the State controls some portion of production and infrastructure, as well as income, and establishes the legal and economic frameworks for private activity. 'The existence of a solid network of independent, nationally-organized organizations is a prerequisite of as much importance for the functioning of the negotiation economy as an effective State.' (Hveem, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990, Chapter 6, p. 169)

A high degree of industrialization and production allows for the existence of wealth to distribute. But this must be accompanied by a strong State, with an established culture and institutions that support growth. The high degree of integration into the global market is an efficient mechanism employed by the Nordic countries to avoid stagnation and rent-seeking. Furthermore, the distribution of national income is confined to personal incomes and consumption, but not to property rights and production decisions, as subsidies on these last two areas disincentivize innovation and efficiency.

According to Sanandaji (2016), the Nordic nations have long depended on a culture that generates economic success and positive social norms. Historical factors can explain why unusually high levels of trust, a strong work ethic, and an emphasis on individual responsibility developed in these cold lands, long inhabited by independent farmers who were generally not subject to feudal systems. 'It is not the welfare state that created high levels of social capital: the relationship is the reverse.' (Sanandaji, 2016)

Furthermore, the participation of the public sector in Swedish industry has always been very small—between 2 and 6% of total industrial employment, excluding natural or technical monopolies such as railways, postal services, and utilities. The basic attitude of both the Swedish government and the unions has been not to nationalize economic activity, but to nationalize the income generated by that activity. What matters is not formal ownership, but efficiency. Today, Sweden thus has one of the relatively smallest public enterprise sectors among industrialized countries.

Additionally, the Scandinavian model demonstrates the importance of maintaining a very active labor policy, in which trade unions act as the driving force. These unions reject protectionist policies and hold a positive attitude toward Swedish companies' investments abroad, driving firms to transform themselves into multinationals.

Furthermore, Scandinavian industrial policy differs from the traditional pro-competitive, antitrust-type industrial policy in that it declares itself in favor of productive efficiency rather than allocative efficiency. This means that it defends economies of scale, the formation of natural monopolies, and their competition in international markets, with the aim of achieving allocative efficiency. (Hjalmarsson, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990)

5. Latin American Development

The disparity in the pace of development between Latin America and the Scandinavian nations between the nineteenth and twentieth centuries is attributable to a series of factors. These include the South American mono-export model, state interventionism, the absence of a pragmatic and technological educational focus, trade unionism in pursuit of rent-seeking, as well as the scarcity of domestic entrepreneurial leaders capable of effectively directing the export and transformation of raw materials.

'The Chilean problem consisted in having based all the progress of national development on saltpeter exports' (Blomström & Meller, 1990, Chapter 3, p. 64). Mono-exporting generated a vulnerable economy in Chile, as well as in Uruguay, Ecuador, and Colombia, bringing with it a Dutch disease from which none has managed to escape. For example, part of the cause of Uruguayan stagnation was that only 4 economic sectors dominated 60% of total production. This type of primary export-oriented economy, without an innovative sector that produces linkages, has impeded the development of the domestic market.

According to Kalmanovitz (2019), the colonial paradigm that prevented self-regulation and trade on the part of the Creoles continues to affect South American economies to this day. The commercial routes available to the Scandinavian countries were inaccessible to Latin American countries due to the Spanish commercial monopoly, headquartered in Cádiz, which obstructed the foundations of trade. Furthermore, internal trade in Colombia and Ecuador was always weak as a consequence of the geographical barriers imposed by the Andean mountain ranges. To this is added a fragile and disorganized political system (Abril-Ojeda, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990).

On the other hand, foreign ownership played a very limited role in Sweden, with only approximately 12% of industrial companies under foreign ownership, and foreign control exercised in only 2% of these. Swedish economic development undoubtedly had nationalist traits. In Chile, by contrast, the abundance of saltpeter was exploited by foreign firms. This follows the enclave hypothesis, which establishes that the sector exploited by foreign investment does not benefit the host economy at all, since few domestic inputs are used and profits are remitted abroad, given the technological, banking, and skilled labor deficiencies required for the national exploitation of resources in Latin America. (Blomström & Meller, 1990)

Additionally, South American governments moved from liberalism to restrictionism at the beginning of the twentieth century, making the public sector a significant controlling agent—though one whose bureaucracy did not generate strong production. From the 1940s, but more particularly in the 1950s and 1960s, multinationals and state-owned enterprises came to play an

increasingly prominent role in industrial development.' (Ocampo, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990)

Latin American protectionism represents an indirect incentive for the collective action of workers, who seek to benefit from the advantages obtained by firms. This leads to the creation of a vigorous union system that, unlike the Scandinavian model, does not typically maintain friendly relations with the government. These unions represent a small group of workers and struggle for a greater share of GDP without concern for the resulting social costs. This characteristic is consistent with the Marxist rhetoric of the union movement, demanding high wages despite low productivity (Rama, cited in Blomström & Meller, 1990, Chapter 5, p. 136). In this way, unions have attempted to obtain subsidies and support, pressuring the State to adopt a Scandinavian-style welfare model, despite the absence of a consolidated industrial or commercial economy.

6. Conclusion

In brief, Scandinavian economic development took off in the mid-nineteenth century thanks to economic liberalism, a liberal credit system, the importation of foreign technology, investment in infrastructure, and production efficiency incentives, along with educational reforms and guarantees of private property. This process follows Rostow's development theory and aligns with the principles of the free market and Adam Smith's 'invisible hand.'

After all, trade played a crucial role as an engine of growth, not only in the export of raw materials, but also in the importation of technology and human capital to train the Scandinavian workforce. The social and economic developments presented in these nations are part of an accumulative process in which each advance reinforces the others.

Additionally, the Nordic historical process was key to enhancing efficiency, supporting the current welfare state. The Latin American experience, by contrast, has been marked by radical political changes due to its colonial tradition, which has impeded self-regulation, the strengthening of trade, and technological advancement. As a result, Latin America has witnessed a system of rent-seeking, with agents that foster social and productive stagnation, remaining in a primary export economy without added value, whose stability depends on foreign activity.

Despite sociological differences, both Latin America and the Scandinavian regions possess abundant natural resources, strategic geographic locations, and human capital. Were Latin America to adopt an approach with greater economic liberalism and undertake a firm struggle against rent-seeking, in addition to investing in the formation of a well-prepared and technically trained workforce, it could replicate the economic success observed in the stages of development of the Scandinavian countries.

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